

Insight #1. Innovating Through Public Procurement: Scope, Rationale, and Methodology for INTERCEPT

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1. About us

Polish Platform for Homeland Security (PPHS), Corvers Procurement Services BV and CORVERS Greece Monoprosopi I.K.E. (collaboratively CORVERS), Kentro Meleton Asfaleias (KEMEA), and DIGINNOV-Digital Innovation Consulting S.R.L. (DIGINNOV) bring together their expertise to drive the success of INTERCEPT. PPHS coordinates the project, leveraging its strong connections with European security practitioners and stakeholders. KEMEA contributes experience in cross-border collaborations in innovation procurement, acting as Lead Procurer, coordinating the User Observatory Group (UOG) and the Group of Public Buyers, and defining the overall procurement strategy. DIGINNOV provides cutting-edge knowledge in technology evaluation, innovation needs, and security applications, ensuring alignment with user requirements and strategic goals. CORVERS specializes in innovation procurement and legal frameworks, providing expert guidance on Pre-Commercial Procurement (PCP) preparation and training for public buyers.

2. Executive summary

Innovation Procurement of Advanced Technologies for Safe Remote Vehicle Stopping by Law Enforcement -**INTERCEPT**- project addresses the growing security threats posed by motor vehicles in Europe, including high-speed pursuits, vehicle-ramming attacks, and criminal activities involving stolen vehicles. Existing law enforcement tools lack the capability to remotely and safely stop vehicles, creating a critical need for innovation. INTERCEPT aims to fill this gap by developing scalable and effective solutions through Pre-Commercial Procurement (PCP), ensuring that technologies align with real-world law enforcement needs.

At the core of INTERCEPT's approach is a demand-driven innovation model, which actively involves Law Enforcement Agencies (LEAs), security experts, and industry stakeholders. This ensures that the project's solutions are based on actual operational needs and challenges, ranging from stopping impaired drivers to preventing terrorist vehicle attacks. The User Observatory Group (UOG) and Group of Potential Buyers (GPB) play a crucial role in providing continuous feedback, helping to refine the project's focus and ensuring that the developed solutions are practical, adaptable, and legally compliant.

INTERCEPT follows a structured PCP framework that fosters competition and collaboration, based on the European Assistance for Innovation Procurement (EAFIP) methodology. The process begins with a needs assessment and a state-of-the-art analysis to define technological gaps, followed by market research and OMCs to engage suppliers and refine requirements. The following steps are into the development of a business case development and procurement strategy formulation to ensure solutions are cost-effective, feasible, and market-ready. To maximize industry engagement, INTERCEPT employs a broad outreach strategy through direct communication, social media, newsletters, and industry collaborations. The project's website serves as a central hub for updates, event announcements, and stakeholder engagement, ensuring continuous participation and transparency.

3. Introduction: Background & Objectives of INTERCEPT

In recent decades, an increasing number of security threats involving motor vehicles, ranging from high-speed pursuits to deliberate vehicle-ramming attacks occurred within the borders of the European Union. These incidents have demonstrated the critical need for innovative solutions to enable Law Enforcement Authorities (LEAs) to effectively mitigate the risks posed by vehicles that threaten public safety. Motor vehicles have been used as tools for crimes, including terrorism, theft, and driving under the influence (DUI), causing substantial harm to citizens and society. These threats have intensified not only in frequency but also in their complexity, requiring coordinated and technologically advanced responses.

Traffic-related incidents remain one of the most dangerous aspects of law enforcement. Traffic stops and high-speed pursuits are particularly hazardous, with law enforcement officers frequently exposed to life-threatening situations. Alarming, 91% of police pursuits arise from nonviolent offences but often result in significant fatalities and injuries to officers, suspects, and innocent bystanders. In 2019 alone, over 22,000 police chases were reported in France, leading to 5,789 accidents and 260 deaths. Such incidents underscore the pressing need for safer methods to manage high-risk vehicle events. Similarly, car theft and DUI incidents continue to burden LEAs, as traditional methods of apprehension often carry substantial risks to public safety and officers alike.

Terrorist attacks using vehicles as weapons to ram into a building, crowd of people, or another vehicle have further intensified the urgency of this issue. Vehicle-ramming incidents have emerged as a relatively low-skill yet devastating tactic, with perpetrators exploiting the accessibility of vehicles to cause maximum harm. These attacks have proven challenging to prevent and have become a prominent security threat across Europe. Deliberate vehicle ramming has also been used in various crimes, including incidents stemming from road rage. In some cases, such acts have been attributed to the driver's psychiatric condition. Additionally, vehicles have been employed by attackers to force entry into secured buildings, such as those with locked gates, before setting off explosives.

Despite the availability of advanced vehicle technologies, such as speed warning systems and collision avoidance systems, existing solutions remain inadequate for addressing the unique challenges faced by LEAs. Current systems lack the universal capability to remotely and safely stop vehicles, leaving law enforcement officers with limited tools to mitigate high-security threats effectively. To bridge this critical gap, the INTERCEPT project has been initiated to provide European LEAs with innovative tools and technologies to remotely and safely stop motor vehicles that pose an imminent danger.

The INTERCEPT project builds upon the results of the i-LEAD project. In February 2023, the representatives of Law Enforcement Agencies of the i-LEAD project - procurement experts and experts in the field of stopping vehicles underscored the absence of a universal electronic or electrical device capable of safely stopping vehicles universally. This gap has driven the need for a coordinated effort to develop new solutions through Pre-commercial Procurement (PCP) actions.

The INTERCEPT project aims to prepare the procurement of research and development services for innovative solutions that will equip European LEAs with effective, reliable, and scalable tools to stop vehicles in a safe and controlled manner remotely. By addressing technological gaps, INTERCEPT reduces security risks while ensuring solutions align with real-world needs through collaboration with security experts and industry stakeholders.

The following sections explore INTERCEPT's innovation targets, the procurement approach, methodology, and use cases, as well as outreach and stakeholder engagement strategies.

3.1. Innovation Aspects of INTERCEPT

The INTERCEPT project is designed to fill a critical gap in law enforcement by developing safe, effective, and scalable methods to remotely stop dangerous vehicles. This critical gap has persisted despite the increasing frequency and complexity of vehicle-related threats.

At its core, the project's innovative essence lies in its use of the Pre-Commercial Procurement (PCP) framework to stimulate research and development (R&D), align the operational needs of European Law Enforcement Agencies with emerging technological solutions and create a sustainable foundation for future security advancements.

Demand-Driven Innovation

A key strength of INTERCEPT is its demand-driven innovation model, ensuring that law enforcement agencies define the problem and influence technological development. By involving LEAs and public procurers from the very beginning, the project prioritises addressing practical challenges faced by LEAs in their daily operations. This demand-driven approach enables public authorities to articulate their requirements in functional and operational terms, creating a framework where innovation stems directly from user needs. By leaving the technical specifics open, private sector stakeholders are given the freedom to develop creative and diverse solutions that meet these clearly defined demands.

The process begins with the identification and analysis of shared needs among practitioners, ensuring that the foundation for innovation is firmly rooted in the challenges they face. Within INTERCEPT, this collaborative effort is driven by LEAs from several EU countries and contributions from the wider practitioner community through the User Observatory Group. Together, they develop security use cases that focus on pressing and high-priority security challenges, such as remotely and safely stopping vehicles that pose imminent threats to public safety. These use cases address critical needs like early detection of potential threats, event monitoring, and the coordinated response of security forces – all tailored to the realities of day-to-day operations.

By continually refining these use cases based on practitioner input and practical constraints, INTERCEPT bridges the gap between conceptual innovation and tangible, real-world applicability. At the end of the project, the consortium will define one common challenge that will guide a future PCP. This challenge will serve as the foundation for continued innovation, ensuring that the demand-driven approach remains central to future developments.

Encouraging Competition and Collaboration

INTERCEPT fosters both competition and collaboration by engaging multiple technology providers through structured PCP phases. This allows suppliers to experiment, prototype, and refine their solutions, ensuring the most effective technologies emerge.

Open Market Consultations (OMC) serve as a platform for direct interaction between public procurers, industry innovators, law enforcement agencies and R&D providers. These consultations create a shared understanding of the security use cases, technological gaps, and operational requirements, providing a fertile ground for aligning public sector needs with private sector capabilities. This collaborative model not only facilitates the development of tailored solutions but also lays the groundwork for the broader adoption and scalability of the innovations developed.

Enhancing Public Buyers' Decision-Making

Another key innovation aspect of INTERCEPT is its focus on empowering EU public buyers with data-driven insights and tools to make informed decisions regarding investments in innovative security technologies. Through comprehensive analyses of the state-of-the-art, INTERCEPT provides a clear understanding of existing solutions, gaps, and emerging technologies. This includes evaluations of Commercial Off-The-Shelf (COTS) solutions, patents, emerging technologies and feedback from industry consultations. By combining market intelligence with practitioner feedback, INTERCEPT ensures that developed solutions are both technologically advanced and operationally viable for deployment across European law enforcement agencies.

Promoting Scalability and Market Uptake

INTERCEPT is committed to ensuring that the solutions developed are scalable and easily adopted by law enforcement agencies across Europe. The project applies [the European Assistance for Innovation Procurement \(EAFIP\)](#) methodology providing ready-to-use procurement templates and guidelines to facilitate adoption and ensuring that the solutions developed through the PCP process are accessible, implementable, and aligned with regulatory and operational requirements. By conducting online and hybrid OMC events, INTERCEPT also raises awareness among

innovators and potential suppliers, bridging the gap between R&D efforts and market readiness. These outreach activities serve to attract new talent, encourage the formation of consortia, and stimulate the creation of new markets for vehicle-stopping technologies.

Building a Sustainable Innovation Ecosystem

Beyond its immediate technological objectives, INTERCEPT aims to create a sustainable ecosystem for innovation in security technologies. The project fosters cross-border collaboration among public buyers, security agencies, and industry leaders, creating an EU-wide network that supports joint procurement and future R&D efforts.

By aligning public procurement strategies with market-driven innovation, INTERCEPT is creating a transformative model for addressing complex public sector challenges. Its focus on early-stage R&D, demand-driven innovation, stakeholder collaboration, and sustainability ensures that the project not only delivers cutting-edge solutions but also establishes a robust framework for future advancements in law enforcement capabilities.

4. How Innovation Procurement Can Tackle the INTERCEPT Challenge

The INTERCEPT project addresses the need for effective, reliable, and scalable tools that enable LEAs to remotely stop vehicles in a safe and controlled manner. To achieve this goal, INTERCEPT employs innovation procurement, specifically the PCP framework, as a strategic approach to stimulate research and development in this critical domain.

Unlike traditional procurement, which focuses on off-the-shelf solutions, innovation procurement fosters the creation of new, advanced technologies tailored to the operational needs of LEAs. PCP is a phased R&D procurement process that allows public authorities, end users, public buyers, and industry stakeholders to drive innovation in fields where no viable market-ready solutions currently exist. This approach ensures that LEAs play an active role in shaping the next generation of vehicle-stopping technologies while promoting competition and collaboration among technology providers.

Traditional procurement approaches focus on acquiring existing products or services that are already available on the market. However, when it comes to vehicle-stopping technologies, no universally effective, scalable, and remotely operable solution is available for law enforcement. Due to the complexity of this challenge, existing technologies may not fully meet law enforcement's operational needs, necessitating further research and development through PCP to explore innovative alternatives. The existing unmet needs foster innovation through early-stage R&D, making PCP the ideal mechanism for defining LEA needs and enabling multiple suppliers to explore and experiment with novel technological approaches.

Through a structured PCP approach, INTERCEPT aims to revolutionise the way European LEAs handle vehicle-related threats, ensuring a safer and more effective response to evolving security challenges.

4.1. Methodology

The INTERCEPT project follows a structured step-by-step approach to prepare a Pre-commercial procurement (PCP), based upon the [European Assistance For Innovation](#)

Procurement (EAFIP) methodology and integrating the experience of KEMEA as Lead Procurer in PCP projects, to set the basis for the development of innovative vehicle-stopping solutions. This INTERCEPT methodology is designed to guide the approach to the PCP process efficiently, ensuring alignment with innovative best practices and the operational needs of law enforcement agencies seeking advanced solutions for safely stopping vehicles remotely. As part of the preparatory stage of the Innovation Procurement life cycle, INTERCEPT will be executed over several steps with multiple feedback and learning loops (Figure 1):

Figure 1: INTERCEPT Innovation Procurement Phases

The figure above illustrates the six phases of the INTERCEPT methodology, structured to guide the PCP process from preparatory actions to the final operational validation of innovative solutions. This approach ensures a well-defined procurement cycle, integrating market engagement, evaluation, and solution development while maintaining user transparency and competitiveness. The methodology aligns closely with the EAFIP methodology, adapting its step-by-step framework to the specific needs of law enforcement agencies.

This process ensures that public buyers actively shape the development of new technologies while fostering competition among suppliers.

EAFIP methodology step-by-step

Figure 2: EAFIP step-by-step methodology

As shown above, in Figure 2, the methodology begins with five key steps that make up the preparatory phase, leading up to the procurement launch: (i) *needs identification and assessment*; (ii) *state-of-the-art analysis*; (iii) *open market consultation*; (iv) *business case development* and (v) *analysis of the procurement strategy and tender documents*. These steps establish a clear foundation for effective procurement and market adoption.

The process begins with *needs identification and assessment*, where INTERCEPT collaborates with European LEAs to define the operational and technical challenges related to vehicle-stopping technologies. This phase involves questionnaires, interviews, round-table discussions, and workshops with security practitioners and stakeholders, ensuring that the project's direction is aligned with real-world requirements. The gathered insights help to shape use cases, ensuring that solutions address high-priority law enforcement challenges. This approach follows the EAFIP methodology, ensuring that procurement decisions are based on clearly defined gaps and validated practitioner needs.

In the following step, INTERCEPT proceeds with the *state-of-the-art analysis* step to examine existing technologies, patents, standards, and COTS solutions. This analysis

evaluates whether current technologies can meet the identified needs or if further R&D efforts are required. LEAs play a key role in this phase by validating security use cases and refining technical requirements, ensuring that the solutions INTERCEPT pursues are practical and deployable in real law enforcement scenarios.

Once the needs and technological gaps are defined, INTERCEPT organises an EU-wide *Open Market Consultation (OMC)* to engage with industry suppliers, technology developers, and security experts across Europe. The OMC serves as a key market engagement tool, validating findings, gathering supplier insights, and fostering industry participation. As part of this effort, INTERCEPT will conduct a series of OMC webinars in multiple European languages (in May 2025), followed by a main OMC event in (in June 2025). These sessions will provide industry stakeholders with an opportunity to understand the project's goals, interact with public buyers, and contribute to the development of innovative solutions. In addition to the webinars, e-pitching sessions will be organised. These sessions will allow each supplier to showcase how their existing or developing technologies can address the procurement challenge, engage in direct discussions with project stakeholders, and participate in multiple sessions to present different aspects of their technology. More information about these events will be made available on the project's website (<https://intercept-horizon.eu/>).

The OMC process begins with the publication of a Prior Information Notice (PIN) on [the Tenders Electronics Daily \(TED\)](#), officially inviting industry stakeholders to participate. To facilitate participation, INTERCEPT will publish the OMC document on the project's website. Additionally, a Request for Information (RFI) questionnaire will be made available via the EU Survey platform, allowing INTERCEPT to collect the market input.

After gathering insights from the OMC activities, an OMC report will be published, summarising key findings while ensuring transparency. The report will make the collected information publicly available while respecting confidentiality of any sensitive data flagged by participating companies.

After the OMC phase, INTERCEPT moves into *business case development* which will involve a comprehensive cost-benefit analysis to assess the comparative value of the proposed solution, justify the selection of PCP over alternative approaches (such as

Public Procurement of Innovative Solutions (PPI), and evaluate its economic impact and market viability. On the other hand, the value calculations will serve as a strategic tool to identify costs, benefits, risks, and financial considerations, ensuring alignment with procurement frameworks, budget planning, IPRs, and potential external funding needs.

The aforementioned steps are followed by the design of the *procurement strategy*, outlining the tendering process, evaluation criteria, IPR considerations, and contract structure. The procurement strategy will be designed in line with the major aspects of the R&D procurement and the results of the preparatory phase, ensuring that a concrete procedure will be employed in line with the EU Treaty principles and the EU procurement legislation.

Additionally, in the context of the project knowledge sharing practices and capacity building in the form of direct training sessions on innovation procurement will be used. The training sessions combining both theoretical information along with empirical cases and interaction, will be delivered to all participating public buyers and practitioners involved as full partners and to those public buyers associated with practitioners who have indicated their interest and are members of the UOG.

Finally, an overall multidisciplinary approach to draw on the knowledge of experts from different domains in security and safety business and economics will be applied throughout the project. This approach will be utilized to analyze, synthesize, and harmonize potential links between disciplines to produce new expertise and methods associated with the project results in a ground-breaking way.

4.2. Use cases

INTERCEPT employs use cases as a framework to explore and address specific vehicle-related security threats, identifying existing gaps and technology deficiencies. By engaging a broad spectrum of stakeholders, INTERCEPT ensures that the most pressing threats are prioritized, with a focus on developing common challenges that drive innovative solutions. The use cases detailed below represent a selection of real-world

scenarios that illustrate the complexity of law enforcement's needs and the necessity for advanced intervention tools.

Use Case #1 – Vehicle ramming attack in a public market: A hostile driver deliberately accelerates a vehicle into a crowded market area, causing casualties and panic. Law enforcement must quickly detect, intercept, and neutralize the threat while ensuring rapid emergency response and minimizing collateral damage.

Use Case #2 – High-speed pursuit in urban surroundings: A suspect flees at high speed through a dense urban environment, endangering pedestrians and other vehicles. Law enforcement must coordinate safe interception strategies, leveraging real-time tracking, predictive analytics, and non-lethal stopping technologies to prevent casualties.

Use Case #3 – Large coach with distressed driver: A coach driver experiences a medical emergency or is incapacitated, leading to a loss of vehicle control. Authorities must intervene quickly to assess the situation, prevent a crash, and ensure the safety of passengers and bystanders through coordinated emergency response.

Use Case #4 – High-speed pursuit following ANPR alert: An Automatic Number Plate Recognition (ANPR) system flags a high-risk vehicle, prompting a pursuit. Law enforcement must decide on an appropriate response, balancing the urgency of apprehension with public safety, using coordinated tracking and intervention tactics.

Use Case #5 – Organized criminal use of high-powered motorcycles and electric bikes: Criminal groups exploit high-speed motorcycles and electric bikes for rapid evasion, robberies, or trafficking. Law enforcement faces challenges in detection, pursuit, and safe interception while considering urban mobility constraints and emerging mobility technologies.

Use Case #6 – Hostage-taking and vehicle ramming: A vehicle is used both as a weapon and a means of hostage-taking, creating a complex threat scenario. Law enforcement must employ specialized intervention strategies to neutralize the attacker, rescue hostages, and mitigate mass casualties while managing public safety risks.

These use cases exemplify the broad spectrum of vehicle-related security threats facing European law enforcement and serve as the foundation for INTERCEPT's efforts to develop effective countermeasures through innovative public procurement.

To ensure a structured approach to defining the common challenge of INTERCEPT, the project follows a three-phase methodology:

Phase #1 - Threat and vulnerability analysis: this phase establishes a foundational understanding of existing law enforcement security processes, legal frameworks, and technological gaps. Data is gathered from INTERCEPT partners and UOG members through workshops and information-sharing sessions, culminating in a consolidated taxonomy of threats and vulnerabilities.

Phase #2 - Use case elaboration and prioritization: building upon the insights gained from the first phase, the project formulates several comprehensive security use cases. These use cases integrate geographic coverage, threat types, technological tools, and response coordination. Stakeholders contribute to prioritization, ensuring that the most pressing security concerns are addressed.

Phase #3 - Common security challenge consolidation: the final phase synthesizes the use cases into a singular, well-defined challenge requiring R&D services to develop an innovative, procurement-ready solution. This process ensures that the final Common Challenge reflects a broad consensus among European law enforcement agencies and maximizes potential procurement adoption.

5. Outreach channels and stakeholder engagement

Outreach channels are crucial to the success of the INTERCEPT project, as they serve as the primary means of communication, engagement, and relationship-building with stakeholders. These channels ensure that the project reaches the right audience, including key decision-makers, end-users, and contributors, providing vital updates, milestones, and opportunities for involvement.

Outreach channels can also play a critical role in gathering feedback, insights, and requirements from diverse stakeholders, which can guide the project to better address real-world needs. By leveraging a mix of digital platforms (e.g. social media, a project website, a newsletter, tools to organise webinars, etc.), direct communication, and public events (e.g. Open Market Consultations, webinars, workshops) these channels create opportunities for collaboration, transparency, and trust-building.

The main communication channels that INTERCEPT will utilise are outlined below:

1- Direct communication channels to engage potential stakeholders

This includes **targeted emails** and **physical or online meetings**. In particular, direct email communication with both existing contacts and also to initiate new relations can be used to reach key audiences such as LEAs, public safety organizations, and security technology providers, with tailored messages highlighting the project's relevance to their specific needs. Additionally, physical or online meetings, such as conferences, workshops, external and internal events, fairs and others, with high-priority stakeholders to discuss their specific needs, expectations, and potential contributions.

2- Project's website (<https://intercept-horizon.eu/>)

It serves as the primary hub for project information, news, resources and updates including a contact form for inquiries, a newsletter signs up widget and an application form to join groups founded by the project that gather external stakeholders, end users and industry players. The website is the primary platform for announcing events related to OMC activities.

3- Social media

Social media platforms (LinkedIn, Threads and YouTube) play a key role in promoting project milestones, sharing insights and engaging shareholders.

4- Newsletters

Regular newsletters keep stakeholders informed about the updates on project progress, share success stories, and announce upcoming events or opportunities for participation.

5- Webinars and online workshops

INTERCEPT hosts webinars and online workshops to provide shareholders with project insights, discuss challenges, and present potential use cases.

6- Open market consultation (OMC) webinars

The OMC webinars bring together public buyers, researchers, and technology providers for focused discussions and collaborative brainstorming sessions.

7- Collaboration with security networks and associations

Engagement with security networks and industry associations strengthens INTERCEPT's outreach efforts by connecting the project with relevant stakeholders.

8- User Observatory Group (UOG) & Group of Potential Buyers (GPB) Engagement

To maximize the reach and effectiveness of the INTERCEPT, the UOGs & GPB have been established as external advisory bodies. The primary function of the UOG & GPB is to provide insights and feedback from an operational perspective, ensuring that the solution developed aligns with real-world needs and constraints.

The UOG & GPB actively participate in workshops and targeted questionnaires to articulate the challenges and requirements of end users. Their feedback shapes security use cases, refines procurement strategies, and ensures technological feasibility. Through a structured analysis of existing solutions and operational gaps, they contribute to the development of an innovation roadmap, ensuring seamless integration into legal, technical, and operational frameworks.

Beyond technical contributions, the GPB is also instrumental in preparing for the future PCP phase. Their early involvement helps establish procurement frameworks, budget planning, and legal considerations, facilitating a smooth transition from R&D to large-scale deployment.

9- Industry engagement

Engaging industry players is another pillar of the INTERCEPT stakeholder strategy, ensuring that market players contribute to and benefit from the development of innovative solutions. To achieve this, the project conducts a Europe-wide call for interest to compile a catalogue of solutions that could support the goal of **remote vehicle-stopping solutions**.

By integrating industry insights at an early stage, INTERCEPT ensures that the procurement process is well-informed, transparent, and conducive to the development of effective vehicle-stopping solutions. Open Market Consultation events will gather insights on technology feasibility, vendor capabilities, and market trends. Regular updates will be shared via newsletters, social media, emails, and the project website. Feedback mechanisms, such as surveys and interactive workshops, will allow stakeholders to share suggestions and concerns. Beyond the initial phases, ongoing communication will ensure continued stakeholder involvement in future activities, including innovation procurement, and strengthening long-term collaboration.

10- SPIN4EIC: Strategic Innovation Procurement program

[SPIN4EIC](#) is an additional outreach channel for INTERCEPT, expanding its engagement with European innovators and technology providers. Powered by the European Innovation Council (EIC), SPIN4EIC connects INTERCEPT with a network of over 6,000 European startups (EIC Beneficiaries), offering a network for collaboration between technology developers and public buyers. This network enables broader market engagement, facilitates stakeholder connections, and enhances the visibility of INTERCEPT's objectives. By integrating SPIN4EIC into its outreach strategy, INTERCEPT ensures greater market reach, increased industry participation, and enhanced opportunities for innovation-driven security solutions.

6. Conclusions

The INTERCEPT project is a comprehensive initiative aimed at preparing the grounds for the development of safe and effective vehicle-stopping technologies for European LEAs. By integrating an innovation procurement strategy, INTERCEPT ensures the sound preparation of a PCP where the solutions being developed are not only technologically advanced but also tailored to the real-world needs of law enforcement. Through setting a solid basis for the PCP methodology, the project fosters early-stage R&D, engaging multiple stakeholders, including LEAs, technology providers, and industry experts, to create effective, scalable, and adaptable technologies.

A key strength of INTERCEPT is its demand-driven approach, where well-defined security use cases that highlight the variety and complexity of vehicle-related threats, from impaired driving and high-speed pursuits to criminal activities involving stolen vehicles, guide the innovation process. The structured phased methodology adopted by INTERCEPT — from needs assessment to procurement strategy— ensures that the project remains focused on delivering practical and impactful solutions.

The success of INTERCEPT hinges not only on its technological and methodological approaches but also on effective stakeholder engagement. By leveraging diverse outreach channels, including direct communication, social media, newsletters, webinars, and open market consultations, INTERCEPT ensures continuous collaboration with all involved parties. The establishment of the UOG and the GPB as external advisory bodies is a pivotal aspect of stakeholder engagement, ensuring that law enforcement agencies' needs and feedback are directly incorporated into the development process. Furthermore, industry engagement, through a structured process of market analysis and e-pitching sessions, guarantees that the project remains aligned with market capabilities and realities.

The interaction between INTERCEPT and SPIN4EIC within the scope of the networking activities, a strategic initiative connecting over 6,000 European startups, further enhances the project's reach and potential impact, particularly in the market

engagement activities. By organising e-pitching sessions and leveraging SPIN4EIC's extensive network of innovators, the project can tap into a wealth of new ideas and solutions, accelerating the development of cutting-edge technologies that address real-world security challenges.

In conclusion, INTERCEPT's success is predicated on a well-rounded approach that combines innovation procurement, stakeholder engagement, and cross-sector collaboration. By maintaining a strong focus on real-world needs, fostering transparency and trust among stakeholders, and ensuring continuous engagement with technology providers, the project is poised to set the grounds for delivering innovative, scalable, and impactful solutions to enhance the effectiveness and safety of law enforcement in Europe. The synergy with SPIN4EIC amplifies INTERCEPT's potential and ensures that remains at the forefront of vehicle-related security technology development. Through these concerted efforts, INTERCEPT is set to make a significant contribution to the future of law enforcement and public safety across Europe.